

Testing the Bergen approach search strings for SDG research mapping, v. 1.2.2

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Summary

Here we document a testing process we have carried out for our Bergen approach search strings for mapping published scientific research related to 10 of the UNs Sustainable Development Goals (*Armitage CS, Bjerkan HM, Byholm LP, Gåsemyr I, Lorenz M, & Seland EH. (2023). Search strings for finding SDG-related research, Bergen-approach. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7241689>*). The aim of this testing was to identify issues that should be fixed in a revision of the search strings.

Precision and recall testing were carried out at the SDG *target* level for the search strings (*topic approach, v1.2.2, Web of Science Core Collection syntax*). Precision levels varied from 69-88 % for each SDG, with most around 80 %. Recall levels varied more, with some SDG strings performing well already, while others needed more changes (SDGs 3, 4, 7 and 11). Publications identified as “not relevant” or not found during recall testing were examined for why they were found/not found by the strings. Issues were tracked, evaluated and addressed during a subsequent revision of the strings (August/September 2023).

Introduction

About this work

This text documents testing we have carried out for our keyword-based search strings created to map published scientific research related to 10 of the UNs Sustainable Development Goals – SDG 1 No poverty, SDG 2 Zero hunger, SDG 3 Good health and wellbeing, SDG 4 Quality education, SDG 7 Affordable and clean energy, SDG 11 Sustainable cities and communities, SDG 12 Responsible consumption and production, SDG 13 Climate action, SDG 14 Life below water, and SDG 15 Life on land. The most recent released version of the search strings can be found on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7241689>). Releases and working versions can also be found on GitHub (<https://github.com/SDGforskning/sdg-strings>).

This work is a product of the project *Bærekraftsforskning for alle – en transparent kartleggings- og gjenfinningstjeneste* ([Sustainable development research for all – a transparent mapping and discovery tool](#)), a project supported by the National Library of Norway. This project is led by the University of Bergen Library, partnered with the libraries at Western Norway University of Applied Sciences and the University of Stavanger. Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke) has contributed with search strings for two SDGs as an external collaborator.

Background

Previous research has shown that different mappings of SDG-"related" research do not give very consistent results ([Armitage, Lorenz & Mikki 2020](#); [Purnell 2022](#)). This is perhaps unsurprising when you consider that there are different ways to interpret what an SDG covers, different viewpoints on which research themes should be counted as "related", different mapping methods, and different

data sources (see our previous work, [Armitage, Lorenz & Mikki 2020](#)). For example, should *SDG 3 Good health* cover all medical research? Does *SDG 13 Climate Action* cover basic climate science? You will probably get different answers depending on who you ask.

Instead of trying to find the "right" answer, we think multiple mappings (which can capture different views of relatedness) are a good idea. But in order for these to have meaning, documentation must explain a) what it is supposed to find (i.e. how the SDG was interpreted and what research is considered relevant), and b) how the mapping is done. We have written our own strings because we believe there is currently a gap for this kind of mapping. We also wanted to provide a database-independent version in Python, which could search in more than English. In short:

- Our strings allow mapping of research to individual SDG targets ("target-level"). This is useful for identifying where a research set is focused within an SDG. They can be combined to examine the whole SDGs ("goal-level").
- We provide two types of strings: *action* and *topic* approaches, which have different interpretations of "relevance".
- The strings are manually curated. They map at the publication-level (rather than journal or subject cluster), using traditional search methods (e.g. matching terms in the titles, abstracts and keywords). The benefit of this is that it is easier to understand why a result is in or out, the drawback that we sacrifice potential additional recall provided by machine learning.
- The strings allow finding of research in both English and Norwegian.
- For each string and target, we document:
 - How we have interpreted which research themes should be considered "relevant" to each SDG target
 - Sources we have used to identify search terms and/or define terminology
 - Choices we have made regarding inclusion/exclusion, interpretations or syntax (e.g. truncation)

For more thoughts about mappings, see also [Rafols, Noyons, Confraria & Ciarli \(2021\)](#)

Aims and challenges with testing

The aim of these tests was to identify issues that should be addressed in a planned revision of our search strings (August/September 2023). We had carried out informal testing under string development but expected that there would be issues that were missed and therefore systematic testing was necessary.

Testing precision and recall for SDG strings is difficult as there does not exist a gold-standard set for what should be considered relevant. Different stakeholders may interpret which research is relevant to an SDG differently. We therefore test our strings against what we have designed the strings to try and find – i.e. this is an internal test asking *are the strings effective and accurate for doing what we say that they do?* The goal of each string (what we think it should do) is described in the published string documentation as an *interpretation* after each SDG target ("we interpret this target to cover research about...").

Methods

We tested search string version 1.2.2 (www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7711561), released March 9th, 2023. Testing was limited to scientific works. As the *topic approach* is the broadest version of the strings (where recall is prioritised) and we expect it to be used most, we decided that this was the most important version to test. The *action* approach is aimed at finding something relevant quickly,

and therefore is expected to have lower recall and higher precision. The testing below was carried out in May-July 2023.

Precision testing

Our *topic* approach strings were run in the Web of Science Core Collection (Clarivate), and the most recent publications downloaded for each target. At least 5 publications were downloaded for each target, making sure that there were at least 50 publications for the whole SDG. Once assembled, this set was then duplicated, and each copy screened by one person for relevance. The two testers then met and went through the publications together with a third person to make a final decision about relevance. The testers were taken from the project group, one of whom was the author of the most recent version of the string.

We consider “relevance” rather strictly, asking the question: Does this research fall under the *interpretation* we have written for this target? Interpretations are documented in the search string documentation. This means that a publication on a theme covered generally by an SDG (e.g. climate change) but not fitting the interpretation for that target (e.g. climate change adaptation) would not be considered relevant. However, we additionally considered whether the work was relevant for the SDG outside that target (giving an idea of whether it was completely outside the scope or not).

Generally we could group how a research publication handled a theme into 4 groups, which were used to aid deciding relevance. The following were assessed based on the titles and abstracts, and in a few cases the full text:

1. The themes in our interpretation are the main themes of the work. – **Considered relevant**
2. The themes in our interpretation are covered in the work, but as an explanatory factor, setting, or consequence of another theme; alternatively, the work might focus on a specific aspect of the theme, for example legal aspects, research on research about the theme, or a method that uses the theme as a test case. - **Considered relevant**
3. The themes in our interpretation were mentioned by the work, but the work is really about another topic. The work has been found by our strings because the theme might be mentioned in an introductory sentence setting the wider context, as a reason for doing the work, or as one of several examples. For example “Plastic pollution is a major problem on land and in the oceans. This work looks at plastic pollution in mountain ecosystems...” would fall into this category when considering relevance to marine pollution 14.1. - **Considered not relevant**
4. The themes in our interpretation are not covered by the work. – **Considered not relevant**

Recall testing

To test recall, we used two sources to find works in alternative ways to search strings. Note that in both cases, we manually screened the results to find relevant publications according to our interpretation (based on the same criteria outlined above in “precision testing”), before testing if they were found by our search strings. Thus these sources were used to find a short-list of potentially relevant works, rather than being used directly:

- 1) We searched using the text of our *interpretation* in the service <https://elicit.org> (from the non-profit machine learning lab Ought; <https://old.elicit.org/faq>) which uses language models (such as GPT-3 Davinci model) to find works, not only matching strict keywords. The aim with this was to find works that might match our interpretation, but don’t necessarily use the same specific terminology as the search strings. Sorting by “relevance” and limiting to after 2015, we downloaded the top results, and the tester picked at least 5 for each target

that matched our interpretation and were covered by Web of Science Core Collection. We then tested whether these were found by our *topic* search strings for that target.

- 2) Sorting by “relevance”, we downloaded the top results found by Dimensions free SDG mapping tool (<https://www.dimensions.ai/>). The tester then picked 25 that matched one of our interpretations for that SDG and were covered by the Web of Science Core Collection. For a couple of SDGs this was difficult due to the noise in the Dimensions results, and fewer than 25 were assessed. We then tested whether these were found by our *topic* search strings for that target.

Results

Precision testing

Most of the strings reached a precision level near 80 %, and for all SDGs issues were identified which could further improve this. The strings for SDGs 3, 4 and 14 had slightly worse precision than the others – in SDG 4 there were several smaller issues. For SDG 3 there were two major issues: 1) an abundance of literature since the covid 19 pandemic which combines varied subjects and “pandemic” terminology, requiring a tightening of terms in the string, and 2) the string for road-traffic injuries allowed research about road-related animal deaths to be found, which we do not consider relevant. For SDG 14, there was a major issue around an acronym that found other marine works (“MPA” for “marine protected area” also finding “marine predator algorithm” and the unit of pressure, “MPa”).

Some of the “target-irrelevant” results for each SDG could be considered relevant for the SDG generally or another target, despite being not fully relevant at target level – this varied between SDGs, but for most it accounts for ca. 2-3 of the non-relevant results (but 10 results for SDG3).

SDG	Target relevant	Comments on major specific issues
SDG 1	42 / 50 (84%)	
SDG 2	46 / 52 (88%)	
SDG 3	45 / 65 (69%)	3.6 found works about animals and air pollution; 3.3 and 3.d had noise caused by works on the pandemic
SDG 4	36 / 50 (72%)	Mainly issues in 4.1 and 4.6, particularly noise around the term “illiteracy” used in other contexts
SDG 7	39 / 50 (78 %)	7.1 had noise from coal + heating terms
SDG 11	43 / 50 (86 %)	
SDG 12	43 / 55 (78 %)	Some unclarity around 12.5 and “resource use efficiency” – currently counted as irrelevant in testing
SDG 13	41 / 50 (82 %)	
SDG 14	35 / 50 (70 %)	14.5 accounted for 4 of the irrelevant results, due to noise from the acronym “MPA”.
SDG 15	52 / 60 (87 %)	

Full results are available in the file “Testing_precision”, available on Zenodo with this document (where Y=relevant at target level, N= not relevant at target level).

Recall testing

The strings varied in recall – most performed well against the Elicit-sourced works, but some performed poorer against Dimensions-sourced works. In particular, SDGs 3, 4, 7 and 11 were relatively low.

Some of the results for each SDG were found for another target in that SDG (so would be captured by the whole SDG string, but not the specific string for that target) - this varied between SDGs, but usually accounted for 2-4 (but up to 9, for SDG12) of the missing results.

SDG	Recall – Elicit results	Recall – Dimensions results	Comments on major specific issues
SDG 1	29 / 35 (83 %)	25 / 25 (100 %)	Missing synonyms in 1.a and 1.b
SDG 2	42 / 50 (84 %)	24 / 25 (96 %)	Investment terms too limited in 2.a
SDG 3	52 / 65 (80 %)	13 / 21 (62 %)	
SDG 4	42 / 51 (82 %)	8 / 20 (40 %)	Some missing terms in 4.a
SDG 7	20 / 25 (80 %)	10 / 27 (37 %)	
SDG 11	33 / 48 (69 %)	16 / 33 (48 %)	11.5, 11.b and 11.c poor recall
SDG 12	42 / 55 (76 %)	27 / 28 (96 %)	12.b poor recall (0/5 found), string too limited
SDG 13	29 / 34 (85 %)	24 / 25 (96 %)	
SDG 14	62 / 65 (95 %)	20 / 26 (77 %)	
SDG 15	56 / 66 (85 %)	20 / 20 (100 %)	15.b and 15.c poor recall

Full results are available in the file “Testing_recall”, available on Zenodo with this document (where Y= recalled by our strings at target level, N= not recalled at target level).

Follow-up

Works identified as “not relevant” or not found during recall testing were examined for why they were found/not found by the strings. Issues were tracked, evaluated and addressed during a subsequent revision of the strings (August/September 2023).